

A NEW HAMILTONIAN SEMI-ANALYTICAL APPROACH TO VIBRATION ANALYSIS OF PIEZOELECTRIC MULTI-LAYERED PLATES

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Abstract. A new Hamiltonian semi-analytical method is established to investigate the free vibration characteristics of piezoelectric multilayered plates. By performing a Legendre Transform, the classical *Lagrangian* functional is recast into a *Hamiltonian* one, so that the resulting variational formulation can be expressed in terms of the displacements and electric potential and their transverse stresses and electric displacement dual variables. Within the framework of this Hamiltonian formalism, the in-plane of the piezoelectric multilayered plate is discretized into two-dimensional *p-type* high-order spectral finite elements while the resulting first-order one dimensional differential system is solved analytically by enforcing the interface continuity constraints. The whole piezoelectric multilayered plate's dynamic stiffness is then built, from which its circular frequencies are computed with the help of the Wittrick-Williams algorithm. A detailed discussion is provided on the implementation aspects, followed by some numerical examples to assess the robustness, accuracy and effectiveness of the proposed method. The obtained results are verified by comparison with published ones based on conventional approaches.

Keywords: Hamiltonian; Semi-analytic; Spectral finite element; Vibration; Piezoelectric; Multilayer; Plate.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, a wide range of industries including automotive, aerospace and marine have focused on smart structures by devoting many research efforts to harvest electrical power from ambient vibrations using new materials such as electromagnetic, electro-elastic or piezoelectric [1]. Among the class of smart materials, piezoelectric ones are often used due to their ease of manufacturing and high-power density. Laminated composite plates constitute one of the most important components in a number of systems such as aerospace vehicles or civil engineering structures due to their lightweight, high strength and high efficiency of load-carrying characteristic. Piezoelectric composite plates are the most representative smart structures that have received an increasing attention. It is generally acknowledged that the coupling characteristics caused by the structural anisotropy of composite piezoelectric laminated plates make it difficult to model these multi-physics systems from mathematical as well as computational points of view [2]. Therefore, there is still a need to explore and develop new robust and high performance numerical models to accurately predict the dynamic response of such smart structures.

Therefore, hereafter, a *semi-analytical* numerical model for the *vibration* analysis of *piezoelectric* laminated *composite* plates is developed based on the *Hamiltonian partial-mixed* variational formulation (VF) that was recently proposed for the free vibrations analysis of elastic multilayered composite plates [3]. The advantage of semi-analytical approaches lies mainly in its dimension reduction characteristic, which allows overcoming the time and memory costs in traditional numerical approaches such as the *finite element method* (FEM). This is done by turning the plate's partial differential equations into a numerically discretized weak form in the in-plane coordinates while maintaining their analytically solved strong form in the thickness one so that the *interface continuity constraints* (ICC) are satisfied exactly. To deal with complex geometry and boundary conditions (BC), the *spectral* FEM is used for the numerical discretization, thereby increasing the computational efficiency of the here proposed approach. However, in free vibration analysis, the equations become transcendental once the ICC are considered. Here, to tackle this issue, the Wittrick-Williams (W-W) algorithm [4] is implemented.

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2.1 Local and Variational Partial-Mixed Formulations

Consider a 3D linear piezoelectric body that occupies a simply connected domain Ω to which a Cartesian global coordinates system (O, x, y, z) is attached. It is bounded by a sufficiently regular boundary surface $\Gamma = \partial\Omega$, with outward unit vector $\underline{\mathbf{n}}$, and is subjected to known surface traction vector $\underline{\mathbf{F}}$ on Γ_F and surface electric charge scalar Q on Γ_Q , with Γ_F and Γ_Q being parts of the boundary Γ . The latter can also support imposed electric potential scalar $\tilde{\varphi}$ on Γ_φ , so that $\Gamma_\varphi \cap \Gamma_Q = \emptyset$ and $\Gamma_\varphi \cup \Gamma_Q = \Gamma$, and mechanical displacement vector $\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{u}}}$ on Γ_u so that $\Gamma_u \cap \Gamma_F = \emptyset$ and $\Gamma_u \cup \Gamma_F = \Gamma$. The electromechanical equations that describe the corresponding dynamic *local* problem are the:

- Cauchy's and Gauss' equations of motion:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Div} \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} &= \rho \underline{\ddot{\mathbf{u}}} \\ \text{Div} \underline{\mathbf{D}} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad \text{in } \Omega \quad (1)$$

Where, $\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$, $\underline{\mathbf{D}}$ are the linear Cauchy stress tensor and electrical displacement (induction) vector, while Div represents the divergence operator, $\underline{\ddot{\mathbf{u}}}$ the acceleration vector and ρ the mass density.

- Mechanical strains-displacements and electric fields-potential relations:

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} &= \frac{1}{2} (\text{Grad} \underline{\mathbf{u}} + \text{Grad}^T \underline{\mathbf{u}}) \\ \underline{\mathbf{E}} &= -\text{Grad} \varphi \end{aligned} \quad \text{in } \Omega \quad (2)$$

With, $\underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$, $\underline{\mathbf{E}}$ being the linear Lagrange strain tensor and electric field vector, while $\underline{\mathbf{u}}$ and φ are the mechanical displacements vector and electric potential scalar. Besides, Grad denotes the gradient operator.

- Converse and direct piezoelectric constitutive equations (*e-form* type):

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} &= \underline{\underline{\mathbf{C}}}^E \underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} - \underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^T \underline{\mathbf{E}} \\ \underline{\mathbf{D}} &= \underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}} \underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} + \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}}^S \underline{\mathbf{E}} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Where, $\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$, $\underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$ are the engineering (Voigt notations) stress and strain vectors, while $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{C}}}^E$, $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}$ and $\underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}}^S$ are the elastic stiffness (at constant electric field), stress piezoelectric and dielectric (at constant strains) matrices.

- Dirichlet (essential) BC:

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{\mathbf{u}} &= \underline{\tilde{\mathbf{u}}} & \text{on } \Gamma_u \\ \varphi &= \tilde{\varphi} & \text{on } \Gamma_\varphi \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

- Neumann (natural) BC:

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}} \underline{\mathbf{n}} &= \underline{\mathbf{F}} & \text{on } \Gamma_F \\ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{D}}}^T \underline{\mathbf{n}} &= -Q & \text{on } \Gamma_Q \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Where, $\underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}}$ denotes the matrix representing the stress tensor.

In order to formulate the reference problem in a generalized way, the following *generalized* displacement $\underline{\mathbf{U}}$, strain $\underline{\mathbf{S}}$, stress $\underline{\mathbf{T}}$ and load $\underline{\mathbf{G}}$ vectors are introduced:

$$\underline{\mathbf{U}} = \begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\mathbf{u}} \\ \varphi \end{Bmatrix}; \quad \underline{\mathbf{S}} = \begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} \\ -\underline{\mathbf{E}} \end{Bmatrix}; \quad \underline{\mathbf{T}} = \begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \\ \underline{\mathbf{D}} \end{Bmatrix}; \quad \underline{\mathbf{G}} = \begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\mathbf{F}} \\ -Q \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

As a consequence, the piezoelectric constitutive equations (3) rewrite as this *generalized* Hook's elastic law-like matrix form:

$$\underline{\mathbf{T}} = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{C}}} \underline{\mathbf{S}} \quad (7)$$

With, $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{C}}}$ being the *generalized* constitutive behavior matrix [5]. Moreover, the Dirichlet and Neumann BC are restated as:

$$\begin{aligned}\underline{\mathbf{U}} &= \underline{\tilde{\mathbf{U}}} & \text{on } \Gamma_U &= \Gamma_u \cup \Gamma_\varphi \\ \underline{\mathbf{T}} \underline{\mathbf{n}} &= \underline{\mathbf{G}} & \text{on } \Gamma_G &= \Gamma_F \cup \Gamma_Q\end{aligned}\quad (8)$$

Here, the *generalized* stress tensor 4th order matrix $\underline{\mathbf{T}}$ is such that $\underline{\mathbf{T}}^T = [\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \quad \underline{\mathbf{D}}]$.

In the case of a piezoelectric layered body with adjoining laminae *perfectly bonded together* and *without internal electrodes*, the generalized displacement vector $\underline{\mathbf{U}} = \{u_x \quad u_y \quad u_z \quad \varphi\}^T$ and transverse surface traction vector $\underline{\mathbf{T}}_z = \{\sigma_{xz} \quad \sigma_{yz} \quad \sigma_{zz} \quad D_z\}^T$ must be *continuous* through the laminate interfaces so that these ICC hold:

$$[\underline{\mathbf{U}}] = \underline{\mathbf{0}} \quad ; \quad [\underline{\mathbf{T}}_z] = \underline{\mathbf{0}} \quad (9)$$

With, $[*]$ denoting the jump in the value of the enclosed quantity across an interface.

The generalized strains vector is split into thickness (z), $\underline{\mathbf{S}}_z = \{\gamma_{xz} \quad \gamma_{yz} \quad \varepsilon_{zz} \quad -E_z\}^T$, and in-plane (p), $\underline{\mathbf{S}}_p = \{\varepsilon_{xx} \quad \varepsilon_{yy} \quad \gamma_{xy} \quad -E_x \quad -E_y\}^T$, contributions as:

$$\underline{\mathbf{S}}_z = \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}} + \underline{\mathbf{D}}_1 \underline{\mathbf{U}} \quad ; \quad \underline{\mathbf{S}}_p = \underline{\mathbf{D}}_2 \underline{\mathbf{U}} \quad (10)$$

Where,

$$\underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}} = \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{U}}}{\partial z} \quad ; \quad \underline{\mathbf{D}}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \partial_x & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \partial_y & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad ; \quad \underline{\mathbf{D}}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} \partial_x & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \partial_y & 0 & 0 \\ \partial_y & \partial_x & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \partial_x \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \partial_y \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Consequently, the *generalized* piezoelectric constitutive equation (7) can be bloc-decomposed as:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\mathbf{T}}_p \\ \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pp} & \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz} \\ \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz}^T & \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz} \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\mathbf{S}}_p \\ \underline{\mathbf{S}}_z \end{Bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

With, $\underline{\mathbf{T}}_p = \{\sigma_{xx} \quad \sigma_{yy} \quad \sigma_{xy} \quad D_x \quad D_y\}^T$ standing for the *in-plane* (p) generalized stress vector.

In the context of the *harmonic* vibration analysis, the time *variable* in (1) is transformed into a radial frequency ω so that the *Lagrange functional* associated to above local equations (1)-(12) can be written as:

$$\mathcal{L}(\underline{\mathbf{U}}, \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}) = \int_{\Omega} L(\underline{\mathbf{U}}, \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}) \, d\Omega - \int_{\Gamma_G} \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{G}} \, d\Gamma \quad (13)$$

Where, the Lagrangian density is:

$$\begin{aligned}L(\underline{\mathbf{U}}, \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}) &= \frac{1}{2} \underline{\mathbf{S}}^T \underline{\mathbf{C}} \underline{\mathbf{S}} - \frac{1}{2} \rho \omega^2 \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{U}} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\underline{\mathbf{S}}_p^T \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pp} \underline{\mathbf{S}}_p + 2 \underline{\mathbf{S}}_p^T \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz} \underline{\mathbf{S}}_z + \underline{\mathbf{S}}_z^T \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz} \underline{\mathbf{S}}_z \right] - \frac{1}{2} \rho \omega^2 \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{U}}\end{aligned}\quad (14)$$

Or, after substituting the decomposition (10):

$$\begin{aligned}L(\underline{\mathbf{U}}, \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}) &= \frac{1}{2} \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{D}}_2^T \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pp} \underline{\mathbf{D}}_2 \underline{\mathbf{U}} + \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{D}}_2^T \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz} \underline{\mathbf{D}}_1 \underline{\mathbf{U}} + \frac{1}{2} \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{D}}_1^T \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz} \underline{\mathbf{D}}_1 \underline{\mathbf{U}} + \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{D}}_2^T \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz} \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}} + \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{D}}_1^T \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz} \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}} + \\ &\quad \frac{1}{2} \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}^T \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz} \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}} - \frac{1}{2} \rho \omega^2 \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{U}}\end{aligned}\quad (15)$$

The Lagrange functional (13) has to be stationary for the admissible solution $\underline{\mathbf{U}}$ so that this VF holds:

$$\int_{\Omega} \delta L(\underline{\mathbf{U}}, \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}) \, d\Omega - \int_{\Gamma_G} \delta \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{G}} \, d\Gamma = 0 \quad (16)$$

The construction of the Hamiltonian *partial-mixed* VF corresponding to Eq. (16) requires first to determine the dual, or conjugate, variable to $\underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}$ (i.e. the generalized momentum $\underline{\mathbf{P}}$). This is achieved from Eq. (15) as follows:

$$\underline{\mathbf{P}} = \frac{\partial L}{\partial \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}} = \frac{\partial L}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{S}}_z} \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{S}}_z}{\partial \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}} = \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz}^T \underline{\mathbf{S}}_p + \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz} \underline{\mathbf{S}}_z \equiv \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z \quad (17)$$

Then, substituting Eq.(10) into Eq.(17) allows to eliminate $\underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}$ according to:

$$\underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}} = \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz}^{-1} \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z - \underline{\mathbf{D}}_1 \underline{\mathbf{U}} - \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz}^{-1} \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz}^T \underline{\mathbf{D}}_2 \underline{\mathbf{U}} \quad (18)$$

The Lagrange functional density (15) thus writes as:

$$L(\underline{\mathbf{U}}, \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z) = \frac{1}{2} \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{D}}_2^T \left(\underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pp} - \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz} \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz}^{-1} \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz}^T \right) \underline{\mathbf{D}}_2 \underline{\mathbf{U}} + \frac{1}{2} \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z^T \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz}^{-1} \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z - \frac{1}{2} \rho \omega^2 \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{U}} \quad (19)$$

Now, the Hamiltonian energy density is now introduced via this Legendre transform:

$$H(\underline{\mathbf{U}}, \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z) = \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z^T \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}} - L(\underline{\mathbf{U}}, \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z) \quad (20)$$

Where, $\underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}$ is here also expressed in terms of $(\underline{\mathbf{U}}, \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z)$ according to Eq.(18). The following *Hamiltonian functional* is then obtained:

$$\mathcal{H}(\underline{\mathbf{U}}, \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z) = \int_{\Omega} [\underline{\mathbf{T}}_z^T \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}} - H(\underline{\mathbf{U}}, \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z)] d\Omega - \int_{\Gamma_G} \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \underline{\mathbf{G}} d\Gamma \quad (21)$$

By taking the variations of the Hamiltonian functional (21) and grouping together the terms relative to the same virtual variable, the following variational equation holds:

$$\int_{\Omega} \delta \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \left(-\underline{\dot{\mathbf{T}}}_z - \frac{\partial H}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{U}}} \right) d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} \delta \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z^T \left(\underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}} - \frac{\partial H}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z} \right) d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma_G} \delta \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T (\underline{\mathbf{T}}_z - \underline{\mathbf{G}}) d\Gamma = 0, \quad \forall \delta \underline{\mathbf{U}} / \delta \underline{\mathbf{U}}_{\Gamma_U} = \underline{\mathbf{0}} \quad (23)$$

Finally, by using Eqs. (19) and (20), the *Hamiltonian partial-mixed VF* writes as:

$$\int_{\Omega} \delta \underline{\mathbf{U}}^T \left(-\underline{\dot{\mathbf{T}}}_z + \left(\underline{\mathbf{D}}_2^T \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pp}^* \underline{\mathbf{D}}_2 - \rho \omega^2 \right) \underline{\mathbf{U}} + \underline{\mathbf{D}}_1^T \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z + \underline{\mathbf{D}}_2^T \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz}^* \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z \right) d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} \delta \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z^T \left(\underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}} - \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz}^* \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z + \underline{\mathbf{D}}_1 \underline{\mathbf{U}} + \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz}^{*T} \underline{\mathbf{D}}_2 \underline{\mathbf{U}} \right) d\Omega = 0 \quad (24)$$

$$\forall \underline{\mathbf{U}} / \underline{\mathbf{U}} = \underline{\tilde{\mathbf{U}}}(\Gamma_U) ; \quad \forall \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z / \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z = \underline{\mathbf{G}}(\Gamma_G) ; \quad (\Gamma_G) \quad \forall \delta \underline{\mathbf{U}} / \delta \underline{\mathbf{U}} = \underline{\mathbf{0}}(\Gamma_U) ; \quad \forall \delta \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z / \delta \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z = \underline{\mathbf{0}}(\Gamma_G)$$

in which the starred matrices are defined as:

$$\underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz}^* = \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz}^{-1} ; \quad \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pp}^* = \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pp} - \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz} \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz}^{-1} \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz}^T ; \quad \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz}^* = \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{pz} \underline{\mathbf{C}}_{zz}^{-1} \quad (25)$$

2.2 Spectral FE discretization

In order to derive the general solution of the vibration problem in hand, the case of a *single-layer* piezoelectric plate is considered in a first step, for which the finite element (FE) in-plane discretization of the previous Hamiltonian partial-mixed VF is introduced. In a second step, this single-layer solution is extended to the *multilayer* case thanks to its dynamic stiffness (DS) formulation as described in the next section. The single-layer domain is thus decomposed into its in-plane area Σ and its thickness h . Let's then suppose that the primary variables $(\underline{\mathbf{U}}, \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z)$ at any point of the domain have the following separable discretization:

$$\underline{\mathbf{U}}(x, y, z) = \underline{\mathbf{N}}(x, y) \underline{\mathbf{U}}^*(\zeta) ; \quad \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z(x, y, z) = \underline{\mathbf{N}}(x, y) \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z^*(\zeta) \quad (26)$$

Where, $\underline{\mathbf{N}}(x, y)$ is the interpolation matrix containing the FE shape functions and ζ refers to the local thickness coordinate relative to the layer, whereas z denotes the global thickness coordinate. Substituting Eq. (26) into the VF (24) leads to its following discretized form:

$$\int_0^h \delta \underline{\mathbf{U}}^{*T} \left(-\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{N}}}_z \underline{\dot{\mathbf{T}}}_z^* + \underline{\tilde{\mathbf{B}}}_z \underline{\mathbf{U}}^* + \underline{\tilde{\mathbf{A}}}_z^T \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z^* \right) d\zeta + \int_0^h \delta \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z^{*T} \left(\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{N}}}_z \underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}^* + \underline{\tilde{\mathbf{A}}}_z \underline{\mathbf{U}}^* - \underline{\tilde{\mathbf{D}}}_z \underline{\mathbf{T}}_z^* \right) d\zeta = 0 \quad (27)$$

Where,

$$\begin{aligned}\underline{\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{N}}}} &= \int_{\Sigma} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}}^T \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}} d\Sigma & \underline{\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{A}}}} &= \int_{\Sigma} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}}^T \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{D}}}_1 + \underline{\underline{\mathbf{C}}}_{pz}^{*T} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{D}}}_2 \right) \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}} d\Sigma \\ \underline{\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{D}}}} &= \int_{\Sigma} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}}^T \underline{\underline{\mathbf{C}}}_{zz}^{*T} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}} d\Sigma & \underline{\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{B}}}} &= \int_{\Sigma} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}}^T \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{D}}}_2^T \underline{\underline{\mathbf{C}}}_{pp}^{*T} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{D}}}_2 - \rho \omega^2 \mathbf{I} \right) \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}} d\Sigma\end{aligned}\quad (28)$$

and \mathbf{I} states for the identity matrix and Σ is the in-plane surface of the layer.

By invoking the arbitrariness of $\delta \underline{\underline{\mathbf{U}}}^{*T}$ and $\delta \underline{\underline{\mathbf{T}}}_z^{*T}$, Eq.(27) allows to reach this first-order differential system:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{U}}}}^* \\ \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{T}}}}_z^* \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}} & \underline{\underline{\mathbf{D}}} \\ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}} & \underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}^T \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{U}}}^* \\ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{T}}}_z^* \end{Bmatrix}\quad (29)$$

together with these BC at the bottom (b) and top (t) surfaces of the layer:

$$\begin{aligned}\underline{\underline{\mathbf{T}}}_z^{*b} &= -\underline{\underline{\mathbf{G}}}_b^* & (\Gamma_G^b) \\ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{T}}}_z^{*t} &= \underline{\underline{\mathbf{G}}}_t^* & (\Gamma_G^t)\end{aligned}\quad (30)$$

Where, the bloc matrices are defined by:

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}} = \underline{\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{N}}}}^{-1} \underline{\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{A}}}} ; \quad \underline{\underline{\mathbf{D}}} = \underline{\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{N}}}}^{-1} \underline{\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{D}}}} \quad \underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}} = \underline{\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{N}}}}^{-1} \underline{\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{B}}}}\quad (31)$$

High-order spectral FE [6] are used in this approach, so that the matrix $\underline{\underline{\tilde{\mathbf{N}}}}$ can be identified with the identity matrix. The governing equations (29) are solved analytically and the corresponding DS matrix is now derived. Equation (29), relative to a given k -layer, can be rewritten in this condensed form:

$$\underline{\underline{\dot{\Psi}}}^k = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{H}}}^k \underline{\underline{\Psi}}^k\quad (32)$$

Its general solution expresses as $\underline{\underline{\Psi}}_{(z)}^k = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^{\underline{\underline{\mathbf{H}}}^k z} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{c}}}^k$, where the classical Taylor series expansion is employed to evaluate the matrix exponential function so that $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{e}}}^{\underline{\underline{\mathbf{H}}}^k h_k} = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{Z}}}_k$. The integration constant vector $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{c}}}^k$ is moreover determined with the help of BC (30). On the one hand, the matrix exponential at the bottom surface $z_b = 0$ reduces to the identity matrix and $\underline{\underline{\Psi}}_{(z_b)}^k \equiv \underline{\underline{\mathbf{c}}}^k$ so that BC (30) gives:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{U}}}_{(k)}^{b*} \\ -\underline{\underline{\mathbf{G}}}_{(k)}^{b*} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{c}}}_1^k \\ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{c}}}_2^k \end{Bmatrix}\quad (33)$$

On the other hand, $\underline{\underline{\Psi}}_{(h_k)}^k \equiv \underline{\underline{\mathbf{Z}}}_k \underline{\underline{\mathbf{c}}}^k$ on the top surface $z_t = h_k$ of the layer so that BC (30) implies:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{U}}}_{(k)}^{*t} \\ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{G}}}_{(k)}^{*t} \end{Bmatrix} = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{Z}}}_k \begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{c}}}_1^k \\ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{c}}}_2^k \end{Bmatrix}\quad (34)$$

Further, Eqs. (33) and (34) allow to eliminate the constant $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{c}}}^k$ so that the DS problem of the k -th layer writes:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{G}}}_{(k)}^{*b} \\ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{G}}}_{(k)}^{*t} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}}_k^{11} & \underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}}_k^{12} \\ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}}_k^{21} & \underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}}_k^{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{U}}}_{(k)}^{*b} \\ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{U}}}_{(k)}^{*t} \end{Bmatrix}\quad (35)$$

with:

$$\begin{aligned}\underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}}_k^{11} &= \left[\underline{\underline{\mathbf{Z}}}_k^{12} \right]^{-1} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{Z}}}_k^{11} & ; & \quad \underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}}_k^{12} = \left[\underline{\underline{\mathbf{Z}}}_k^{12} \right]^{-1} \\ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}}_k^{21} &= \underline{\underline{\mathbf{Z}}}_k^{21} - \underline{\underline{\mathbf{Z}}}_k^{22} \left[\underline{\underline{\mathbf{Z}}}_k^{12} \right]^{-1} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{Z}}}_k^{11} & ; & \quad \underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}}_k^{22} = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{Z}}}_k^{22} \left[\underline{\underline{\mathbf{Z}}}_k^{12} \right]^{-1}\end{aligned}\quad (36)$$

3 SOLUTION PROCEDURE

The analytical integration of the set of two-point boundary value problem (35) allows us to obtain the DS of a given layer in terms of its bottom and top surfaces variables. A procedure is now required to assemble this layer DS into a global one by enforcing ICC as well as the plate's edges BC. With the global DS at hand, the unknown circular frequencies are finally evaluated by solving a transcendental algebraic system, which is done with the help of W-W algorithm [4].

3.1 Application of the plate's BC

In the context of piezoelectric multilayer structure modelling, the issue of enforcement of the ICC is a difficult task. Straightforward fulfilment of the transverse stresses and electrical displacement variables ICC at the laminate interfaces is usually done in the framework of mixed VF. Therefore, thanks to a partial Legendre transformation, a four-field partial-mixed VF has been established in the previous section so that it inherits the algebraic properties of Hamiltonian matrices, facilitating the numerical implementation of ICC. However, the detailed inspection of this partial-mixed VF shows that it suffers from inconsistencies when dealing with arbitrary BC of the plate's edges. Namely, one can show that for BC other than the simply supported one, there is not anymore a one to one correspondence between the primary and conjugate nodal variables; the application of BC thus makes the final matrix rectangular so that the problem turns to be unsolvable. Here, in order to handle arbitrary BC i.e. any combination of simply supported, clamped and free BC, the boundary nodal variables have to be split into prescribed and unknown ones. This is formally equivalent to consider given BC and reactions at the plate's edges. The crux point of the proposed approach is that the identification of these two types of variables is done before integrating the equations along the thickness direction. The elimination of the prescribed degrees of freedom (DOF) is then performed by bearing in mind that the final resulting matrix must be square.

3.2 Dynamic stiffness computation and Wittrick-Williams algorithm's implementation

The problem is correctly formulated whatever the plate's edges BC as soon as the final equations write in the form of a first-order differential system equation with a square underlying coefficients matrix. The well-known W-W algorithm [4] can now be applied to compute the natural circular frequencies ω of the multilayered plate once the DS of the whole plate is formulated as before. The algorithm basically allows to compute the number of modes when ω is lower than a given trial radial frequency ω^* . The W-W algorithm originates from the Sturm sequence property for constrained systems and it states that the eigenvalue count $\mathbf{J}(\omega^*)$ is given by:

$$\mathbf{J}(\omega^*) = \mathbf{J}_0(\omega^*) + s \{ \underline{\mathbf{K}}(\omega^*) \} \quad (37)$$

Where, $\underline{\mathbf{K}}(\omega^*)$ is the DS of the whole plate and $s \{ \underline{\mathbf{K}}(\omega^*) \}$ is the signature of $\underline{\mathbf{K}}(\omega^*)$; that is, the number of its negative diagonal elements after an upper triangularization. Moreover, $\mathbf{J}_0(\omega^*)$ is given by:

$$\mathbf{J}_0(\omega^*) = \sum_{k=1}^N \mathbf{J}_0^k(\omega^*) \quad (38)$$

Where, $\mathbf{J}_0^k(\omega^*)$ refers to the number of eigenvalues in the frequency range $[0, \omega^*]$ when the upper and lower surfaces of the plate's k -th layer are clamped. The evaluation of $\mathbf{J}_0^k(\omega^*)$ is a crucial point to be fixed for applying the method. An explicit formulation of $\mathbf{J}_0^k(\omega^*)$ is actually out of reach in general, except for very basic systems with few DOF. Thus, a numerical evaluation of $\mathbf{J}_0^k(\omega^*)$ is adopted here. For this, we consider that a given plate's k -layer is made of a certain number of M sufficiently *thin numerical sublayers* so that no vibrations occur inside any of these s -th thin sublayer when its external faces are clamped. Under this hypothesis, we can state that:

$$\mathbf{J}_0^{k,s}(\omega^*) = 0, \quad \forall s = 1:M \quad (39)$$

$\mathbf{J}_0^k(\omega^*)$ is then computed *recursively* by assembling each thin sublayer's DS $\underline{\mathbf{K}}_k^s$ into an overall DS $\underline{\mathbf{K}}_k(\omega^*)$ for the k -th layer. $\mathbf{J}_0(\omega^*)$ is next calculated thanks to Eq.(38) and $\mathbf{J}(\omega^*)$ is evaluated with the help of Eq. (37) after assembling each layer's DS $\underline{\mathbf{K}}_k(\omega^*)$ into an overall one $\underline{\mathbf{K}}(\omega^*)$.

Now the eigenvalues count $\mathbf{J}(\omega^*)$ for a given radial frequency range $[0, \omega^*]$ is known, the well-established bisection method can be implemented to determine all circular frequencies within this range without missing any.

4 NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

In this section, some numerical tests are presented to assess the performance of the proposed new Hamiltonian semi-analytical approach for vibration analysis of piezoelectric multilayered plate. For this, two test cases are considered: in order to show the convergence and accuracy of the present approach, the vibration analysis of a homogenous cantilever piezoelectric plate is first performed [7]; then, the test case of a fully clamped piezoelectric multilayer cross-ply plate is analyzed [8]. The numerical tests are performed with a fixed 2x2 high-order spectral FE mesh with variable number N (up to 8x8 per element) of Gauss-Legendre-Lobatto grid points.

4.1 Single layer piezoelectric cantilever rectangular plate

Consider a single layer piezoceramic cantilever plate having these e-form electromechanical properties: $C_{11} = 107.6$ GPa, $C_{12} = 63.12$ GPa, $C_{13} = 63.85$ GPa, $C_{33} = 100.4$ GPa, $C_{44} = 19.62$ GPa, $C_{66} = 22.24$ GPa, $e_{31} = -9.6$ N/Vm, $e_{33} = 15.1$ N/Vm, $e_{15} = 12$ N/Vm, $\varepsilon_{11}/\varepsilon_0 = 1110$, $\varepsilon_{33}/\varepsilon_0 = 852$, $\varepsilon_0 = 8.85 \cdot 10^{-12}$ F/m, $\rho = 7760$ kg/m³. The plate has a rectangular shape and its dimensions along x , y , z are $a=20$ mm, $b=40$ mm and $h=1.5$ mm. The electric BCs are short-circuit ones; that is, $\varphi=0$ on the upper and lower plate's surfaces. A comparison is made with experimental and 3D ABAQUS FEM results [7]. Table 1 lists the results obtained with increasing orders of spectral elements; the numbers between brackets show the errors defined as: Error (%) = (Present-FEM)/FEM. As one can see, a good agreement is observed in comparison with 3D FEM results. The table shows also that 6th order spectral element is sufficient to compute the third mode. Moreover, convergence is achieved with a 4th order element when computing the first two modes. This confirms the good performance of the present semi-analytical approach in conjunction with W-W algorithm to compute the natural frequencies of a vibrating piezoelectric plate.

Table 1: Convergence analysis for a cantilever single layer rectangular piezoelectric plate (Hz)

Mode	[7]		Present			
	Exp.	FEM	2x2	4x4	6x6	8x8
1	2940	2905	2910 (0.17)	2909 (0.14)	2907 (0.06)	2908 (0.1)
2	3270	3233	3321 (2.72)	3238 (0.15)	3235 (0.06)	3235 (0.06)
3	7320	7243	7448 (2.83)	7291 (0.67)	7250 (0.1)	7250 (0.1)

4.2 Five layers cross-ply piezoelectric fully clamped square plate

A fully clamped (CCCC) square piezoelectric laminate of thickness $h = 0.01$ m and side length a is now analyzed. The plate's lay-up consists of a (0°/90°/0°) Graphite-Epoxy sublaminates bonded by two PZT-4 outer layers. Each piezoelectric layer has a thickness of $0.1 h$ whereas each elastic composite layer has a thickness of $0.267 h$. Three geometric configurations with side-to-thickness ratios $a/h = 4, 10$ and 50 are analyzed. The relevant materials properties are: $E_1 = E_2 = 81.3$ GPa, $E_3 = 64.5$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = 0.329$, $\nu_{13} = \nu_{23} = 0.432$, $G_{12} = 30.6$ GPa, $G_{13} = G_{23} = 25.6$ GPa, $e_{31} = e_{32} = -5.20$ Cm⁻², $e_{33} = 15.08$ Cm⁻², $e_{15} = e_{24} = 12.72$ Cm⁻², $\varepsilon_{11}/\varepsilon_0 = \varepsilon_{22}/\varepsilon_0 = 1475$, $\varepsilon_{33}/\varepsilon_0 = 1300$ for PZT-4 and $E_1 = 132.38$ GPa, $E_2 = E_3 = 10.756$, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.24$, $\nu_{23} = 0.49$, $G_{12} = G_{13} = 5.654$ GPa, $G_{23} = 3.606$ GPa, $\varepsilon_{11}/\varepsilon_0 = 3.5$, $\varepsilon_{22}/\varepsilon_0 = \varepsilon_{33}/\varepsilon_0 = 3.0$ for Graphite-Epoxy. The electric potential at all edges around the plate is specified to zero; the plate's upper and lower surfaces are also grounded. However, the inner surfaces of the piezoelectric layers are assumed non-electroded so that the electric potential and transverse electric displacement are continuous at the interfaces. Table 2 compares the fundamental radial frequency (in rad/s) computed by the present approach with those of [8], obtained by a spline finite strip method. It is observed that the converged results for the herein proposed approach are in close agreement with the reference ones. Moreover, thanks to the analytic integration of Eq. (32) along the thickness direction, the present approach does not exhibit the shear locking phenomena for high side-to-thickness ratio. Figures 1 and 2 provide the through-thickness distributions of some primary variables to show the ability of the present approach to satisfy the ICC without any post-processing.

Table 2: Fundamental Circular frequency (rad/s) of a CCCC piezoelectric square cross-ply $[0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]$ plate

Method	$\omega/100$ in rad/s		
	$a/h=4$	$a/h=10$	$a/h=50$
[8]	69.804	19.924	1110.5
Present (8x8)	69.895	19.906	1111.7
Error (%)	0.13	-0.09	0.11

Figure 1: Fundamental mode cross-thickness distributions of $u(\frac{a}{2}, \frac{b}{2}, z)$ and $\varphi(\frac{a}{2}, \frac{b}{2}, z)$, $\frac{a}{h} = 4$ for a five plies multilayered CCCC square plate.

Figure 2: Fundamental mode cross-thickness distributions of $\sigma_{yz}(\frac{a}{2}, \frac{b}{2}, z)$ and $D_z(\frac{a}{2}, \frac{b}{2}, z)$, $\frac{a}{h} = 4$ for five-ply multilayered CCCC square plate..

5 CONCLUSIONS

This work presents a new approach for the vibration analysis of piezoelectric multilayered plates. The formulation leads to a partially-mixed Hamiltonian VF. The in-plane dimensions are discretized with 2D High-

Order FEM whereas the solution along the thickness is expressed analytically using a matrix exponential function. W-W algorithm is then implemented to compute the natural frequencies of the piezoelectric composite plate. A comparison with reference solutions from the literature highlights the accuracy and fast convergence of the proposed approach.

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